

Access to Finance and Firm's Performance: Evidence from West Africa

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Abstract

The study assesses the impact on access to finance on firms' performance in West Africa by employing a generalized linear model based on Enterprise survey data for 15 West African countries. The study concludes that access to finance has a negative impact on firms' performance in West Africa. The business environment in which firms are situated has a significant impact on their performance. Firms in West Africa encounter some challenges in securing funds to grow their businesses due to the unfavourable business climates such as corruption, court administration constraints, tax rates, unstable electricity supply as well as an unfair competition that are not properly regulated. Therefore, firms should seek patient funds that could allow them ample time to grow.

Keywords: Access to finance; Firms' performance; West Africa; Generalized linear model

1. Introduction

Small and Medium-scale Enterprises (SMEs) have become apparent which is now recognized with much attention worldwide. This is a result of the critical role SMEs play in the creations of employment, creativity and innovation which results in the sustainable development of international economies. The role of SMEs in national economic development cannot be overemphasized especially in income generation and distribution, capital accumulation, employment generation, poverty reduction and the empowerment of people especially women (Lisa, 2009).

Micro, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises are socially and economically important as they represent 99 percent of an estimated 19.3 million enterprises in the EU and provides around 65 million jobs representing two-thirds of all employment (World Bank, 2010). Also, SMEs are described as an efficient prolific job creator, the seed of businesses and the fuel of national economic engines (Abor and Quartey, 2010). In recent years, access to finance has been identified as one of the most hindering issues on the growth and sustainability of SMEs in developing countries. SMEs are considered the main pillars of most countries. In most African countries, SMEs represent over 90 percent of the firms and account for 50-60 percent of employment in these countries. African countries are noted to be largely disadvantaged in financial development (Allen et al., 2011; Beck et al., 2009; Fowowe, 2013). Therefore, this financing gap in firm financing is most likely to be a bigger problem for Sub-Saharan Countries Especially those in West Africa than countries in other developing regions. Most industry players have come to agree that if all stakeholders are to show much commitment to the development of the SME sub-sector, then the economy must necessarily witness a rise in its transformation and prosperity.

With the many merits of SMEs, their major hindrance to growth and development appears to be access to finance. According to Mensah, (2004) there are many who believe that the single most important factor inhibiting the growth of the SMEs sector is the lack of finance. There are a lot of factors that account for lack of finance. Some of these include those identified by the World Bank (2003). These factors include distortions in the financial sectors, lack of know-how on banking part, information asymmetry (access to business information), and high risk in lending to small businesses. In recent times, the importance of finance the growth and sustainable development of SMEs in West-Africa has been a major concern to many stakeholders. This is because for West-Africa to be able to strive to in gaining a spot in the world economic environment, its SMEs

should mature and transform into a gateway where adoption to the systematic production approach becomes easier.

SMEs sector within Sub-Saharan Africa has been referred to as the 'Missing Middle' in the context of financial inclusion or access to financial (including banking) services. (P.Quarthey et al. 2017). Many studies have come to conclusions that SMEs provide the highest source of employment in West Africa and the world as a whole. Thus SMEs need to be seen growing at a pace that provides that provide assurance of generating employment (by going into labour production), a rise in incomes/earnings which in the end will result in reducing poverty and yield economic development. If the needed financial support for these enterprises becomes available for investment, then it will culminate in the growth of SMEs in West Africa. The paper is motivated by this essential factor of financial inclusion or access to finance to investigate the impact of access to finance on firms' performance in West Africa as well as the effect of their constraints on performance.

The paper intends to contribute to the literature in the field of access to finance and firms' performance to provide a solid ground for academic perusal and policymaking. This study makes use of recent firm-level data from the World Bank which is based on responses from enterprises on diverse constraints that they face in the day-to-day running of their businesses and also in relation to their accessibility to financial markets.

The paper is categorized into section 1 which is the introduction, section 2 which contains the literature review, section 3 reports the methodology and data collection, section 4 consists of the results and discussions, and finally section 5 which concludes the study.

2. Literature Review and Hypotheses development

2.1 Access to finance and firms' performance

The critical role SMEs play occupies a greater portion of the economic land scope of most economies Worldwide, this is seen predominantly in the developing countries. It is estimated that more than 95 percent of enterprises across the world are SMEs and they account for approximately 60 percent of private-sector employment (Ayyagari et al., 2011). One of the central tenets of the vast literature on finance growth nexus is that finance promotes growth by channeling credit to the most eligible firms and there is a lot of macroeconomic evidence which shows that financial development enhances the overall growth of the economy (Levine, 2005).

Many studies view SMEs from an economic perspective. However, enterprises are not just suppliers but also consumers. They play an important role if they are able to position themselves in a market with purchasing power: their demand for industrial or consumer goods will stimulate the activities of their suppliers, just as their own activities are stimulated by their clients (Anthony & Thomas, 2012). In addition, demand is important to income-generation potential of SMEs and their ability to stimulate the demand for both consumer and capital goods (Berry et al., 2002). Within West Africa, the World Bank's distance to the frontier index of 2014 shows that with the exception of Ghana and Nigeria, all other West African countries were at best 60 percentage points from New Zealand (the best-performing country in the world). While Ghana and Nigeria were about 35 and 40 percentage points from the frontier respectively, Ghana's index was higher than the average for OECD high income and Europe and Central Asian Countries (World Bank WDI,2015) ,as cited by (P.Quatey et al., 2017). SMEs account for a greater share of businesses in South Africa, Ghana and Nigeria (Abor and Quarthey, 2010; Gbandi and Amissah, 2014) and their contribution to GDP, in Ghana for example, stood at about 40 percent in 2012 (PWC, 2013).

With regards to the perking order theory, preferably the best resort for firms to fund their business operations as working capital is reliance on internal funds before they intend to look out for external funds through issuance equity instruments for long term debt (Boundless, 2014). In spite of the many challenges that cripple firms' performance, access to finance is mostly a severe challenge due to its capacity to inject more blood into the life

of firms. As an engine for growth for every business, access to finance typically hampers the propensity of firms' capacity to grow and flourish (Steel & Webster, 1991; Aryeetey et al., 1994), in spite of this, access to finance potentially and significantly impact firms' performance (Gockel & Akoena, 2002). So hypothesis 1 is developed as follows:

H1: Access to finance positively and significantly affects firms' performance.

2.2 Finance constraints, access to finance and firms' performance

A critical look at the previous studies on SMEs as cited by (P. Quartey et al., 2017) reveals that inadequacy of funds significantly constraints SMEs development (Aryeetey, 1994; WorldBank, 1994; Parker et al., 1995; Arthur, 2003; Mensah, 2004; Deakins et al., 2008; Okpara, 2011). According to Dinh et al.'s (2012), 38 Sub-Saharan African Countries were selected for their study and their results indicated that electricity was a top ranked constraint in 16 Countries while access to finance was top-ranked in 11 countries (see B. Fawowe, 2017). Finance is said to be the "glue" that holds together all the diverse aspects involved in small business start-ups and development (Green et al., 2002). However, potential providers of finance, whether formal or informal, are unlikely to commit funds to a business that they view as not being on sound footing, irrespective of the exact nature of unsoundness (Anthony K. Ahiawodzi and Thomas C. Adade, 2012).

Among the constraints that firms encounter in pursuit of business success and performance are insufficient financing, managerial incompetence, lack of advance equipments, poor infrastructures, uneasiness to capital market, regulatory constraint, unfavorable tax regimes etc. (Sowa et al., 1992; Aryeetey et al., 1994; Osei et al., 1993; Bani, 2003). Fawowe (2017) studied the impact of access to finance on SMEs' performance in Africa, with much emphasis on the business and finance constraints he concluded that the constraints encountered by firms in their operations have a negative force which derails them from the path of business success to employ more people in Africa. To account for this run down, it means that there is a significant relationship between finance constraints, business constraints and firms' performance hence these hypotheses;

H1: There is a significant relationship between finance constraints, business environment constraints and performance of firms.

H2: There is a significant impact of access to finance, access to finance constraints and business environment constraints on firms' performance.

2.3 Access to finance, firms' characteristics and performance

In examining the financial intermediation process, it is important to note that, because the supply of credit is inexhaustible, there will always be some borrowers whose demand for credit risk is not satisfied in full or terms they consider inappropriate (Hall, G., 1996). Collier (2009) as cited by (P. Quartey et al., 2017), indicates that the lack of access to finance by SMEs in Africa is, unfortunately, a result of two high risk characteristics. First, the provision of finance for Africa is generally rated as riskier than for other regions. Secondly, the provision of finance for small firms is globally rated as riskier than for large firms.

Several new studies such as Beck T. et al. (2005), Ayyagari et al. (2008), Aterido and Hallward-Driemeier (2010), Aterido et al. (2011), and Dinhet al. (2012) have strictly used firm-level data to investigate access to financial markets and other constraints that affect firm performance.

The center of attention for this study is dedicated to the West African countries which have been shown to have less financial development when compared with other countries in other regions. Thus, the study will help in understanding how a boost in the financial sector and a better functioning of it will strengthen the growth of West African firms. Many previous studies were based on subjective data which has a high possibility of it being influenced by an essential difference of the respondents. This study makes use of recent firm-level data

from the World Bank which is based on responses from enterprises on diverse constraints that they face in the day-to-day running of their businesses and also in relation to their accessibility to financial markets.

Scores of studies have found that the major obstacles that firms are faced with are mostly determined by the characteristics of the firms thus the age of the firm, size of firm, ownership, the gender of management etc. (Beck et al., 2003; Silva & Carreira, 2010; Schiffer & Weder, 2001). In addition, Demirgiic-Kunt and Maksimovic (2003) posit that the smaller the size of firms the higher the benefit of “property right protection” (Beck et al., 2004). Moreover, small size firms and their cashflow have a relationship which very significant to maneuver the financial constraints of the films. In lieu of this, the study develops this hypothesis to unravel the relationship that exists between access to finance, firms' characteristics and performance. So we get the following hypothesis.

H4: Access to finance and firms' characteristics significantly affect firms' performance.

I.

3. Research Design

3.1 Research data and measurement

The study used data from the Enterprise survey dataset from the World Bank. The World Bank with its associates conducted the survey which covered data of small, medium and large enterprises across the globe. The data was obtained from many cross-country surveys across several years with an objective of access to finance and its constraints by SMEs. The study used data collected from 15 West African countries. The variables used for the study are as follows:

(1)Firms' performance

Firms' performance can be measured in two-folds, thus financial and non-financial. As the study uses a survey data which gathered non-financial measure, it settles on employment growth which also a non-financial measure of firms' performance.

The employment growth is the percentage increase of people employed over the survey period.

(2) Access to finance

As the study's objective is to assess the impact that accesses to finance has on performance, it uses the subjective measure of access to finance from the Enterprise Survey categorized into firms with bank loan/credit line, firms with bank loan as working capital, firms with investment from banks.

It is measured on a scale of 0 and 1, where 1 means the firms use any of the three access to finance measures and 0 means No.

(3)Business environment constraint

This variable is a subjective measure of business environment constraint gathered in the Enterprise Survey and categorized into electricity constraint, telecommunication constraint, water constraint, informal sector competition, corruption, court administration constraint, tax rates, tax administration constraint, crime/theft, business regulation constraint.

They are measured by a scale of 1 – 5, where 1 stand of no obstacle, 5 stands for the severe obstacle.

(4)Access to finance constraint

Access to finance constraint of firms is to measure the hindrances that push away firms to get access to finance in the credit accessibility climate and they are subjective measures gathered from Enterprise Survey Database.

They are measured with a scale of 1 – 5 where 1 stands for no obstacle, 5 stands for the severe obstacle.

(5) Firms characteristics

Firms' characteristics are involved in assisting in controlling for the divergent effects that could arise in the difference of characteristics or conditions of firms in the process of access to finance and the impact on the firm's performance.

Firms' characteristics include female ownership, female manager, firms size (small, medium, large) enterprises.

3.2 Methodology and Model specifications

The study applied econometric methodology to analysis the data to make its statistical inference. The econometric methodology used is generalized linear model (GLM). The econometric model for the study can be written as follows:

$$FP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{Access to finance})_i + \mu_i \quad (1)$$

$$FP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{Access to finance constraint})_i + \beta_2 (\text{business environment constraints})_i + \mu_i \quad (2)$$

$$FP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{Access to finance})_i + \beta_2 (\text{Access to finance constraint})_i + \beta_3 (\text{business environment constraints})_i + \mu_i \quad (3)$$

$$FP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{Access to finance})_i + \beta_2 (\text{Access to finance constraint})_i + \beta_3 (\text{firms characteristics})_i + \mu_i \quad (4)$$

In the models 1 to 4, β_0 represents the intercept, access to finance constraint represents firms that answered that they are constraint by access to finance, business environment constraints represents the constraints faced by firms in their daily operations (such as electricity constraints, water constraints, corruption, crime, court constraints, tax rate, tax administration constraints, business regulation constraints and competition constraints), access to finance represents the source of finance available for firms thus firms with credit or loans from banks, firms with bank loan as working capital and firms investments funded by banks, firm size represents small, medium and large enterprises; where μ represent the error term or disturbances and i represent the cross section of countries.

3.3 Descriptive statistics

The summary statistics of the variables for the study can found in table 1 and it reports that the mean and the median are closely related whiles the standard deviation is homogenous in nature. The skewness test confirms that the majority of the variables are negatively skewed and the kurtosis test also reports positive and leptokurtic. The Jarque-Bera test confirms that the majority of the variables are not in a normal distribution. firms' average performance for the sample period stood at 2% annually, the sizes of firms grew at an annual rate of 2.813%, 2.845% and 2.595% as in large, medium and small respectively. However, firms that used bank credit to cushion their business operation had an average growth rate of 2.855% and firms that used bank loans for investment had an average growth rate of 2.649% annually with the sample period. Meanwhile, firms that used bank loans as working capital grew at an annual rate of 2.945%.

Table 1 Summary statistics of access to finance, firm size and performance

	Firms performance	medium	small	large	bank credit line	bank invest	bank_wc
Mean	2.001	2.845	2.595	2.813	2.855	2.649	2.945
Median	2.020	2.845	2.588	3.001	3.133	2.960	3.116
Maximum	2.986	3.487	2.885	3.456	3.745	4.009	3.945
Minimum	0.833	2.460	2.230	0.000	0.993	-0.357	0.095
Std. Dev.	0.562	0.228	0.174	0.794	0.793	0.986	0.914
Skewness	-0.225	1.083	-0.339	-2.971	-1.141	-1.717	-1.903
Kurtosis	2.886	5.417	2.891	11.296	3.375	6.512	7.006
Jarque-Bera	0.144	7.023	0.314	69.430	3.566	16.080	20.362
Probability	0.931	0.030	0.855	0.000	0.168	0.000	0.000

4. Results and discussions

4.1 The impact of access to finance on firms' performance

the study examined the impact on access to finance on firms' performance as the main objective and table 3 reports the results. it is evidenced in table 3 that access to finance in West Africa has a negative relationship or impact on firms' performance with a coefficient of -0.347, -0.224 and -0.290 at 5% and 10% statistical significance level. However, a percentage increase in firms' access to finance as loans or credit lines from banks will lead to a 0.347% decrease in firms' performance. Also, a percentage increase in firms with investment by banks will lead to a 0.224% decrease in firms' performance as in employment growth. Notably, a percentage increase in firms with working capital from banks will lead to a 0.290% decrease in firms' performance.

Table 2 Access to finance and firms performance

Access to finance and firms performance	coefficient	t-statistics	p-value
firms with Credit/loan from banks	-0.347	-2.99	0.009**
constant	2.992	9.06	0.000***
firms with investments by banks	-0.224	-2.06	0.058**
constant	2.594	8.03	0.000***
firms with working capital from banks	-0.290	-1.97	0.067*
constant	2.855	6.2	0.000***

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level, * indicates 10% significance level

4.2 Access to finance, access to finance constraints, business environment constraints and performance

In every economy, the business climate or environment has a significant impact on firms' performance as well as access to finance opportunities. However, the study aimed at assessing the impact these two dynamics have on the performance of firms in West Africa. Table 3 reports that the results of the analysis performed and can be reported that access to finance constraints have a negative and statistically significant impact on firms' performance in West Africa. Perhaps, it is only in model 2 that access to finance showed an insignificant impact where firms make an investment with bank facilities. In addition, the business environment constraint also showed some significant impact on firms performance; electricity constraint, competitor constraint, corruption, court administration constraint and tax rate, all showed negative and statistically significant impact on firms' performance in West Africa whiles water constraint, transportation constraint and tax administration constraint showed positive and statistically significant impact on firms' performance in West Africa but business regulation constraint showed insignificant relationship with firms' performance. Most importantly, access to finance in West Africa showed a negative and statistically significant impact on firms' performance. Literally, a

percentage in access to finance will lead to 1.249%, 0.676 and 7.814% decrease in firms' performance with regards to employment growth.

Table 3 Access to finance, access to finance constraints, business environment constraints and performance

Access to finance, constraints and performance	1	2	3
Access to finance constraint	-1.315 (-4.71)***	0.222 (0.66)	-0.722 (-5.03)***
electricity constraint	-4.012 (-5.30)***	-4.597 (-4.18)***	-3.736 (-7.73)***
water constraint	0.409 (2.26)**	0.500 (1.55)	0.342 (2.67)**
competitor constraint	-2.943 (-2.22)**	-4.486 (-2.32)**	-3.922 (-4.47)***
transportation constraint	4.447 (3.80)**	5.867 (3.30)**	4.388 (5.81)***
crime constraint	1.330 (2.43)**	2.102 (2.50)**	1.548 (4.26)***
corruption constraint	-5.522 (-3.30)**	-6.932 (-2.619)**	-6.198 (-5.39)***
court constraint	-2.432 (-4.55)***	-3.019 (-3.34)**	-2.331 (-6.41)***
business regulation constraint	0.182 (0.88)	0.009 (0.03)	0.139 (1.11)
tax rate constraint	-3.230 (-2.73)**	-5.108 (-2.93)**	-3.889 (-5.12)***
tax administration constraint	7.325 (3.58)**	8.865 (2.80)**	7.544 (5.49)***
firms with Credit/loan from banks	-1.249 (-12.00)***		
firms with investments by banks		-0.676 (-6.64)***	
firms with working capital from banks			-7.814 (-18.54)***
constant	30.309 (4.71)***	32.143 (3.49)**	32.379 (7.47)***

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level. T-statistics are in parentheses

4.3 Access to finance, constraint, firms characteristics and performance

Another objective of the study is to assess the impact of access to finance on firms' performance by controlling the relationship with access to finance constraints and firms' characteristics. However, the analysis performed confirms that there is an insignificant impact of access to finance on firms' performance by taking into consideration the constraints firms encountered in the process of securing access and the characteristics of the firms.

Table 4 Access to finance, constraint, firms characteristics and performance

	1	2	3
Access to finance constraint	-0.159 (-0.56)	-0.264 (-0.72)	-0.376 (-1.75)
female ownership	-0.069 (-0.10)	0.363 (0.54)	-0.080 (-0.11)
female manager	0.160 (0.16)	-0.340 (-0.31)	0.253 (0.23)
firms with Credit/loan from banks	-0.411 (-1.45)		
firms with investments by banks		-0.225 (-0.72)	
firms with working capital from banks			-0.432 (-1.45)
constant	3.574 (3.31)**	3.625 (3.54)**	4.325 (5.17)***

Note: ** indicates 5% significance level, * indicates 1% significance level. T-statistics are in parentheses

4.4 Access to finance, firms characteristics and performance

To assess the impact that accesses to finance has on firms' performance by controlling the effect with firms' characteristics and size; table 8 below displays the outcome of the analysis. From the table, it is evidenced that medium-size firms showed a negative relationship with their performances Generally, access to finance and the other characteristics showed an insignificant impact on performance.

Table 5 Access to finance, firms characteristics, size and performance

	1	2	3
female ownership	0.243 (0.29)	0.484 (0.70)	0.236 (0.30)
female manager	-0.209 (-0.15)	-0.510 (-0.41)	-0.202 (0.30)
small	0.379 (0.53)	0.314 (0.36)	-0.042 (-0.05)
medium	-1.243 (-2.64)**	-1.384 (-2.05)**	-0.957 (-1.71)
large	0.067 (0.20)	0.111 (0.40)	0.209 (0.83)
firms with Credit/loan from banks	-0.175 (-0.84)		
firms with investments by banks		-0.654 (-0.24)	
firms with working capital from banks			-0.259 (-0.97)
constant	4.821 (2.86)**	5.117 (3.38)**	4.960 (3.53)**

Note: ** indicates 5% significance level. T-statistics are in parentheses

5. Conclusion

The study assessed the impact of access to finance on firms' performance in West Africa and it used survey data from Enterprise Surveys data sourced from the World Bank. The study employed the econometric methodology to perform its analysis.

The study found that access to finance in West Africa has a negative impact on firms' performance in line with Babajide (2017) and the size of firms thus small and large has an insignificant impact on firms performance while the size as in medium enterprises have negative and statistically significant impact on firms' performance. The characteristics of firms as in female ownership and female as managers of a firm have an insignificant impact on firms' performance. The business environment in which firms are situated has a significant impact on their performance. Firms in West Africa encounter some challenges in securing funds to grow their businesses due to the unfavourable business climates such as corruption, court administration constraints, tax rates, unstable electricity supply as well as an unfair competition that are not properly regulated.

The study recommends to firms' to seek external funds or patience fund which could give the firms ample time growth due to the negative impact that funds provided by the banking sector exert on their performance. Ideally, the study found that insufficient funding of firms in West Africa has dire consequences on firms' performances which mostly affects their ability to employ and also generate sales revenue. However, governments should create an enabling environment which support the rapid growth of SMEs to generate employment and promote economic growth.

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